

**RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TOP MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES AND
EXTERNAL CRISIS MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES IN SRI LANKAN
CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY**

Sarathchandra L.D.T.N.¹, Senthilrajah T.²

¹School of Engineering and Built Environment, Birmingham City University, UK

²Faculty of Information Technology and Science, International College of Business and
Technology, Sri Lanka

thamalinayanathara95@gmail.com

Abstract

The Sri Lankan Construction Industry (SLCI) is suffering from crises that are generated from external factors. Crisis Management (CRM) success or failure depends on top management decisions. The lack of studies regarding external CRM (ECRM) in SLCI, generates knowledge gaps and risks to SLCI. Hence, determining the relationship between Top Management Strategies (TMS) and ECRM Strategies (ECRMS) in SLCI is necessitated to survive construction organizations during external crisis periods. Online questionnaire survey was used to collect quantitative data relevant to ECRMS and TMS. 101 SLCI industry participants joined for quantitative data gathering. Pearson correlations test is used to identify linear relationships between TMS and ECRMS. It revealed that ECRMS has moderate positive linear relationships with TMS. Hence, organizations can apply those TMS strategies for increasing effectiveness of ECRM. The final outcomes of the study will be facilitated to smooth operations during external crises in large scale main contractors' organizations registered under the Construction Contractors Grading Schema of the Construction Development Authority of Sri Lanka.

Key Words: External Crises, External Crisis Management Strategies (ECRMS), Top Management Strategies (TMS) and Sri Lankan Construction Industry (SLCI)

Introduction

A crisis can be defined as an unpredictable event that can potentially generate negative outcomes (Park, 2017) for an individual, a group or an organization. Construction organizations are easily affected by crises due to high initial investments that increase huge financial losses (Sahin, Ulubeyli and Kazaza, 2015). Crisis creates sudden changes to organizations which encourages the necessity of forming new systems to manage crises. Several environmental and organizational factors influence creation crises. Economic, political, technological, legal, and natural factors are key reasons for external crises (Nassar and Erzaij, 2023). Sri Lankan Construction Industry (SLCI) is one of the most innovative, dynamic, and technologically advanced industries among other industries (De Silva, Darmicka and Fernando, 2014). Although, SLCI is suffering from several external crises such as terrorism, natural disasters, economic and financial crises, political instability, and competitions generating from foreign contractors' involvement etc.

CRM can be defined as the dynamic and continuous process used to identifying, planning and resolving of crisis by application of both reactive and proactive actions (Nassar and Erzaij,

2023). CRM success or failure depends on top management decisions. Top management should consider several factors to effective crisis management such as; focusing on financial aspects of crisis, maintaining information flow, tackling information flow bottlenecks, developing flexibility of managerial strategies, monitoring and managing interpersonal relationships (Sahin, Ulubeyli and Kazaza, 2015).

SLCI is suffering from external crises. And identification of effective CRM strategies and processes necessary to smooth running of construction organizations. Lack of studies regarding external CRM (ECRM) in SLCI, generate knowledge gaps and risks to SLCI. Hence, determining relationship between Top Management Strategies (TMS) and External Crisis Management Strategies (ECRMS) in SLCI is necessitated to surviving during the external crisis periods.

Research findings were focused only on external crises situations in SLCI. The findings can be only applied to large scale main contractors’ organizations in SLCI which are registered under C3, C2, C1, CS1 and CS2 as per the Construction Contractors Grading Schema of Construction Development Authority of Sri Lanka. This study only focused on TMS and ECRMS.

Methodology

The quantitative Research Methodology approach was applied to determine the linear relationship between TMS and ECRMS in SLCI. Several three ECRMS and four TMS applied during external crisis periods were identified through the literature sources. As per the operationalization Table 1, the online survey developed by using Google Forms. All these strategies were measured by using five point Likert scale; 1-Strongly Disagree, 2-Disagree, 3-Neutral, 4-Agree and 5-Strongly Agree.

Table 1 – Operationalization Table for Online Questionnaire Development

Concept	Measures	Question Number in Questionnaire
ECRMS	M1. Crisis management plan preparation	2.1
	M2. Decision making framework	2.2
	M3. Organization’s resource management	2.3
TMS	M1. Maintain behavioral change	3.1
	M2. Monitoring and supervision	3.2
	M3. Organization overhead controlling	3.3
	M4. Motivation	3.4

A Linear relationship between identified TMS and ECRMS was investigated for fulfilment of research objective. ECRMS is considered as a Dependent variable. TMS is considered as Independent variables. The Person Correlation was conducted by developing below null and alternative hypotheses as Table 2.

Table 2 - Hypothesis for Identification of Linear Relationship between TMS and ECRMS in SLCI

Purpose	Hypotheses
Identify linear relationship between ECRMS and TMS	<p>H₀ – there is no any significant linear relationship between top management strategies and external crisis management strategies.</p> <p>H₁ – there is a significant linear relationship between top management strategies and external crisis management strategies</p>

Present study focused on SLCI employees which are currently working in Sri Lanka. The below criteria used to define the population.

1. Employee should be worked in SLCI as a representative of client, contractor, consultant or subcontractor.
2. Employee should not be minor staff, skilled labour or unskilled labour in construction firm.

Simple random sampling technique used to identify sample of the online questionnaire survey (Osievskyy, Shirokova and Ritala, 2020).

Figure 1 - Minimum Sample Size Calculation for Online Questionnaire Survey by Using G*Power Software

G*Power software is recommended for sample size calculation (Kang, 2021). Minimum sample size requirement for questionnaire survey was determined through for G*Power (version 3.1.9.4) software as Figure 01. The minimum sample size for online questionnaire survey should be 84. The power of rejecting hypothesis is 80%.

Results and Discussion

Sample Description

101 SLCI experts were participated in online questionnaire data collection process. The details of designations are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Graphical Presentation of Participants’ Designation in Online Questionnaire Survey

Figure 3 - Graphical Presentation of Online Questionnaire Survey Participants’ Construction Industry Experience Level

As the figure 4, Majority of respondents (75.25% of respondents) were working in large scale construction organizations which mentioned in research limitations.

Figure 4 - Graphical Presentation of Online Questionnaire Survey Participants' Organizations Categories

Identification of the linear relationship between ECRMS and TMS

The main intention of this analysis is to identify the linear relationship between TMS and ECRMS. Pearson correlation test is widely used to measure the strength of the linear relationship between two variables. Several Correlation coefficient values indicate the strength of the linear relationship between variables. Those values are listed in Figure 5.

Correlation coefficient value (r)	Strength of linear relationship
$r = +1$	Perfect positive linear relationship
$0.7 < r < 1$	Strong positive linear relationship
$0.3 < r < 0.7$	Moderate positive linear relationship
$0 < r < 0.3$	Weak positive linear relationship
$r = 0$	Zero linear relationship
$0 < r < -0.3$	Weak negative linear relationship
$-0.3 < r < -0.7$	Moderate negative linear relationship
$-0.7 < r < -1$	Strong negative linear relationship
$r = -1$	Perfect negative linear relationship

Figure 5 - Correlation Coefficient Values' Indications (Akoglu, 2018)

Significance level (α) in Pearson correlation result use to test hypothesis. If $\alpha < 0.05$, there is enough evidence to reject null hypothesis (H_0) (Supena, Darmuki and Hariyadi, 2021). Hypotheses analyses for this study are shown below.

Pearson correlation test results for ECRMS and TMS are shown in Figure 6.

		ECRMS
TMS	Pearson Correlation coefficient (r)	0.365
	Significance level (α) (2-tailed)	<0.001
	Numbers	101

Figure 6 -Pearson correlation test results for ECRMS and TMS

The α value = < 0.001 which was less than 0.05 was less than 0.05. Hence, there was enough evidence to reject H0. Due to that, there is a significant linear relationship between ECRMS and TMS. The r value = 0.365 which was in between r range of 0.3 to 0.7. Hence, there is a moderate positive linear relationship between ECRMS and TMS.

Effect of crisis increases natural tension in organizations and decrease ability to cope with changes. Continuous monitoring is necessary to maintain these kinds of behavioural (Sahin, Ulubeyli and Kazaza, 2015). Top management decisions can be made for managing complex situations by monitoring the relationship between organizational complexity and employees' behaviours (Daniel and Daniel, 2018). Continuous monitoring is necessary to identify external facilities that are required in CRM. Team distraction can occur due to close supervision. Hence, senior management should consider the organization's managerial size for effective monitoring and supervision (Choi, Sung and Kim, 2010). Evidence of previous studies revealed that monitoring and supervision key strategies in CRM. Organizations can achieve benefits during crises through employees' motivation (Sahin, Ulubeyli and Kazaza, 2015). Any actions which are decrease morale of employees should not be taken in crises situations (Taneja, 2014). Closing organization departments, employees' salaries reduction, given unpaid vacations, restrictions in extra services and employees dismissal are some overhead management strategies that top management implied to CRM as a reactive approach. Those strategies are only suitable for short-term and small-scale CRM. Those strategies caused to loss of experienced employees to organization (Sahin, Ulubeyli and Kazaza, 2015) and the reduction of employees moral. Evidence of previous studies revealed that monitoring, supervision and motivation are key strategies in CRM. Overhead management is not acted in a key role in ECRM. But, the TMS is necessity to effective ECRM. It revealed that the positive moderate linear relationship between ECRMS and TMS.

Conclusion and Recommendation

SLCI is now experiencing multiple external crises. Hence, it is imperative to determine the relationship between TMS (Top Management Strategies) and ECRMS (External Crisis Management Strategies) in order to ensure the resilience of SLCI in times of external crises. The study obtained quantitative data from 101 participants of the SLCI by utilizing Google Forms. The primary objective of quantitative data collection was to ascertain the linear relationship between TMS and ECRMS.

The Pearson correlation test was employed to identify of linear associations between TMS and ECRMS. The analysis demonstrated that there is a moderate positive linear relationship between ECRMS and TMS. Hence, it is advisable to implement such TMS tactics to enhance the efficiency of ECRM. Furthermore. Implementing efficient TMS will enhance the construction organizations' resilience during external crises.

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